

THE IMPACT OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES ON REMOTE MONITORING OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS

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Abstract: The article discusses the use of innovative technologies for farmers and clusters operating in the agricultural sector, focusing on the application of these technologies for growing agricultural products in greenhouses and other closed environments, as well as monitoring their production. This includes the use of automatic irrigation, climate control, temperature, humidity, nitrogen, potassium, and phosphorus level measurement devices, providing nutritional support, fruit ripening methods, and irrigation equipment. Fertilization, determining soil composition parameters, and the possibility of using an automatic control system designed for the cultivation of each agricultural product based on these parameters are highlighted.

Keywords: innovative technologies, management, database, agriculture, precision farming, smart agriculture, smart greenhouse.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the regulation of land and water relations in agriculture, the effective use of agricultural land, the introduction of innovative technologies into the sector, the reduction of low-yield cotton and grain fields, the production of high-yield, exportable products, and the increase in the purchasing price of agricultural products for state needs have all contributed to ensuring the financial stability of agricultural enterprises. Today, with the rapid development of all sectors of society and the state, reforms must be carried out based on modern innovative ideas, developments, and technologies that will ensure the rapid and high-quality development of our country to join the ranks of world civilization leaders.

For this reason, as in all sectors of the economy, agriculture in our country is also undergoing fundamental reforms, implementing market mechanisms, improving the processing system of agricultural products, and creating added value. Significant results are being achieved in these areas. Long-term, forward-looking new tasks for the development of the sector are being outlined. In particular, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 28.01.2022, No. PD-

60, the Strategy for the Development of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 is set, with the aim of creating a people-oriented state by elevating human dignity and further developing civil society [1].

It is planned to increase crop yields and improve labor productivity in all types of land plots in Uzbekistan, in compliance with modern requirements, using innovative methods for agricultural crops. The establishment of a single database to monitor remotely via installed sensors, and the scientific and technical results carried out by research institutions, scientists working there, farmers, and individuals involved in agriculture is also envisaged.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The research focuses on the wide implementation of scientifically-based innovative technologies, the creation of new high-yield, export-oriented vegetable and horticultural crop varieties at research institutions, and the application of advanced foreign experience. It includes the development of automated systems for remote control using energy-saving sensors, signal digital transmission, and microelectronic complexes, as well as the creation of a database, the development of a free platform for collecting, transmitting, processing, and visualizing data from industrial equipment via the internet, and establishing mutual relations with business from an innovative perspective.

In the research of economists in our country, the term "innovation" has become widely used in connection with the transition to market relations. A number of economists studying the problems of innovative development in the agricultural sector, such as A.A. Abduganiyev, A.V. Vakhobov, A.M. Qodirov, S.S. G'ulomov, Yo.A. Abdullayev, Ch. Murodov, T.X. Farmonov, O.P. Umurzoqov, N.S. Khushmatov, A. Muxtorov, and others, have conducted significant scientific research. Thus, summarizing the above definitions, the concept of innovation can be described as follows: Innovation is the introduction of a new or significantly improved product (goods, services), process, a new method of marketing, or a new organizational method in organizing work places or external relations [3].

Foreign scholars such as N.G. Pasyukova and A.S. Kukushkin have focused on the promotion of agriculture in ensuring food security in regions. However, the research of the aforementioned scholars has not sufficiently explored the production of major agricultural products, forecasting, and the socio-economic problems in this sector. From this point of view, the modeling of agricultural production processes, the development of the sector in different regions, state support for the sector, and the forecasting of its future remain urgent issues [4,5].

The United States ranks first in the world in terms of agricultural efficiency, with only 2% of the country's workforce engaged in this sector. In the Netherlands,

"digital technologies" are widely used in agriculture, including the use of "Internet of Things" (IoT) devices to help manage various agricultural processes. In Israel, given the severe shortage of irrigation water, high intensity and efficiency have been achieved through software, irrigation systems, and innovative harvesting equipment. In the Republic of Korea, the experience of innovative agricultural development is unique and can be used in developing countries to ensure food security and form innovative agricultural systems. In Taiwan, high results have been achieved in the last 5 years in developing software and mobile applications and in creating large-scale training programs for farmers. In Argentina, a system for monitoring soil conditions, data collection, and analysis has been implemented. In India, attention is being paid to the introduction of mobile applications such as Agri Value Added Services, which provide farmers with information on weather, product prices, the best technologies for growing crops, and other related issues to improve farmers' knowledge.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Agricultural monitoring equipment and software tools, sensor-based data exchange algorithms, monitoring systems, and mobile application algorithms are considered as part of the research.

The main goal of the research is to manage and monitor the total agricultural production, farming, and livestock products created in the country based on intelligent technologies. As a result of the research, an automatic control system software and technology have been developed for monitoring the development of agricultural products grown in greenhouses and other closed areas for farmers and clusters working in the agricultural sector. This system includes monitoring activities such as automatic irrigation, fertilization, determining the parameters of soil composition, and growing specific agricultural products based on these parameters [6,7].

Research methods include climate control, temperature and humidity measurement instruments, tools for measuring nitrogen, potassium, and phosphorus levels, providing nutrients, determining fruit ripeness, and using irrigation methods.

The scientific significance of the research lies in the development of methods and algorithms for monitoring agricultural lands and the crops grown on them by using satellite data for remote assessment, enabling rapid and accurate evaluation of their conditions [8].

The practical significance of the research is to create and implement software systems that replace imports for monitoring agricultural crops on various land plots.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis shows that the tools currently used in state and city governance practices do not provide an entirely acceptable level for ensuring the supply of agricultural products to the population in Uzbekistan. Some of the demand for food products is met through imports. Taking this into account, the introduction of "Smart Greenhouses" is deemed appropriate for the current objectives. A "Smart Greenhouse" is a fully automated system [10].

One of the key features of smart greenhouses is the ability to install the system's components into any greenhouse, even one that was built previously.

The smart greenhouse includes the following systems:

1. Automatic irrigation system with drip irrigation;
2. Automatic soil temperature maintenance system;
3. Automatic soil restoration system;
4. Auto-ventilation system;
5. Automatic lighting system.

Due to drip irrigation, water is directly delivered to the plant roots. Irrigation occurs in small doses, applied individually to each plant. This method is implemented through multiple network systems in the irrigation system, delivering water by dripping. As a result, the upper layer of soil remains constantly moist, allowing the plants to receive the required amount of water.

The advantages of drip irrigation are as follows:

- The absence of the spread of weeds;
- Uniform water distribution in the soil;
- Water conservation (approximately 30% more efficient compared to traditional irrigation methods).

The disadvantages of this type of irrigation include:

- Relatively complex design;
- Higher equipment costs;
- Continuous monitoring of water purity is required.

Properly calculating the economic feasibility of the heating system is crucial, as the cost of electricity can play an important role in the system's efficiency. The irrigation reservoir can also be equipped with an electric pump and float to regulate the water level in the reservoir. With the introduction of an automatic filling system for the reservoir, this system can be considered fully automated. In the "Smart Greenhouse" system, automatic soil heating is not critical, as its temperature is controlled based on the data set in the thermostat.

Figure 1. Smart Greenhouse Control Systems

The soil heating system includes the following components: a temperature regulator and a heating element. The thermostat allows you to maintain the temperature within the range of +5 to +45 degrees Celsius. Thus, the initially set temperature is established and maintained (Figure 1).

The ventilation process in greenhouses is achieved by opening the leeward side, avoiding the negative effects of cold wind. However, due to new research in this area, the opening of two transoms located on both sides of the greenhouse simultaneously has been implemented. This method not only adjusts the CO₂ level and air humidity but also maximizes control of the warm airflow inside the greenhouse.

For the automatic irrigation system, the following components are required: a water level sensor, which determines the current water level in the reservoir and detects when additional water is needed (based on the soil moisture sensor). In this way, the system can determine when to start the irrigation process.

To monitor soil moisture and observe the irrigation system's operation, an LCD display is used. The microcontroller transmits the received data to the control device, and upon receiving the signal, the water supply system is activated. The irrigation system's functions and settings are controlled by the system, which also includes an alert mechanism to notify about water shortages and display relevant information.

The automatic ventilation system uses the following elements: a temperature and soil moisture sensor. Based on the readings from this sensor, the current state inside the greenhouse is determined. After receiving a signal from the microcontroller, the control mechanism activates the ventilation system.

For the automatic soil heating system, the following components are required: a soil temperature sensor (contact type). After receiving a signal from the microcontroller, the load control mechanism is activated, and the system adjusts the

soil heating process. After these adjustments, the system starts the soil heating. Soil temperature monitoring and the heating process are displayed on the LCD.

All smart greenhouse systems are controlled using an Arduino-series Atmel microcontroller. The Arduino microcontroller has the necessary capabilities for control, including power monitoring, signal transmission, and full control of timing and durations.

The main advantages of this microcontroller include: a 16 MHz processor, 32KB of flash memory, and 2KB of RAM. It also has 20 input/output pins, including 6 analog-type pins. It supports PWM signals on 6 digital pins and has 2 interrupt pins. There are numerous pre-made libraries available in the software environment. The Arduino environment is user-friendly, and it is easy to learn the C++ language with its IDE. When connected to USB power, the Arduino can operate using its 5V power supply (which is sufficient for powering most sensor boards). Additionally, the microcontroller is affordable (Figure 1).

The I2C module solves the issue of limited pin availability by allowing up to four connections. It also features a trimmer resistor, making it easy to adjust the light levels.

To monitor soil temperature changes, a soil surface and soil temperature sensor are used. The sensor detects temperature variations ranging from -10°C to $+40^{\circ}\text{C}$. This selection of temperature indicators is linked to the thermostats discussed above, which operate within these limits, and there is no need for temperatures higher than 40°C in the soil heating system. The measurement error is minimal, and the sensor provides highly accurate readings. The power supply voltage is 5V. The data obtained from the DS18B20 temperature sensor is transmitted to the microcontroller using a one-wire interface. This protocol uses a single communication line, allowing multiple sensors to be used simultaneously.

For controlling PWM signals, the most optimal option is the MOSFET transistor, as its switching state is controlled by current and voltage, similar to a bipolar transistor. This feature allows the Arduino pins to control large currents with small currents, managing the load effectively [3].

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the scientific research, the following conclusions and recommendations can be made regarding the use of the findings:

An analysis of existing approaches and methods for land plot design in the software environment (land plot identification, placement of devices, sensor identification, and plant variety analysis) was carried out. The analysis results indicate the need to develop and improve existing methods and algorithms to ensure real-time data exchange under various conditions and equipment. A comparative

analysis was conducted to determine the land composition and identify suitable plant varieties based on each tool. As a result, it was found that the necessary fertilizers, chemicals, and efficient water usage methods can be identified for plant care, reducing excess costs, and their application can guarantee at least a 30% increase in yield [3].

Additionally, advanced systems are being introduced in the production and sales chains of agricultural products, leading to the creation of opportunities for collecting large volumes of electronic data. Labor productivity increases by 30%, and the necessary practical skills for full crop production are acquired. Conditions are created for the development of stress-resistant, high-yield, transport-adapted, and bioactive-rich crop varieties. "Smart" agriculture allows differentiated use of excessive treatments and chemicals on crops in the field.

Through "smart devices," control and monitoring processes can be automated, significantly reducing human involvement. The application of such technologies in agriculture is evident in areas such as crop farming, "smart" farms, "smart" greenhouses, raw material management, agricultural product storage, agricultural transportation, big data, and more.

For fruits and vegetables, "smart warehouses" allow for real-time monitoring of product conditions (designated temperature, humidity, carbon dioxide levels) using specialized algorithms during storage, helping in making correct decisions. If conditions are violated, the system corrects the situation and notifies the warehouse owner of the changes.

The technological solutions developed for processing and storing agricultural products, as well as the automation of these processes, reduce costs for employees and improve the storage conditions for the harvested crops.

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